

CHEMISTRY OF SUBSTITUTED RING COMPOUNDS.

PART II. SYNTHESIS OF $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ - AND $\alpha\gamma\gamma$ -TRIMETHYLCYCLOPENTANONES

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Several trimethyl *cyclopentanones* have been synthesised. One of these is obtained from *isophorone*, which is reduced to dihydroisophorone and is subsequently oxidised. The trimethyladipic acid thus obtained is cyclised to a ketone which appears to be a mixture. *p*-methylcyclohexanone is methylated to trimethylcyclohexanone, which on oxidation gives $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipic acid; this is cyclised to $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone. A third trimethylcyclopentanone has been synthesised from $\beta\beta$ -dimethyl- γ -acetylbutyric acid through its cyanohydrin and its corresponding lactonic acid, which on reduction gives $\alpha\gamma\gamma$ -trimethyladipic acid. This acid on cyclisation gives $\alpha\gamma\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone. This ketone is found to be identical with that obtained from Clemmenson reduction of dimedone.

Some years ago one of us (M. Q. K.) in course of his studies on the Clemmenson's reduction of cyclic 1:3-diones obtained a monocyclic ketone from dimethyldihydroresorcinol which was different from the ketone obtained by Crossley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 117; 1907, 91, 80) and therefore it was presumed to be a new form of dimethylcyclohexanone (Qudrat-i-Khuda, *Nature*, 1933, 132, 201). Elucidation of the constitution of the ketone was not then complete as the study included a thorough examination of the mechanism of reduction when Dey and Linstead published a paper on the same subject and claimed the ketone obtained by the reduction of dimedone to be trimethylcyclopentanone (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1063). Our observation also points towards the same fact, and in elucidation of this, however, a number of experiments was undertaken which are now embodied in the present communication.

It is interesting to note that by the reduction of dimethylcyclohexane-dione by Clemmenson method, the first product apparently is a bridged bicyclic dione, which at the second stage undergoes pinacolone transformation and the resultant unsaturated ketone is then further reduced to one saturated homologue (III).

But a second portion of the dimethyldihydroresorcinol undergoes normal process of reduction and is converted into dimethylcyclohexane (IV, R = R' = H).

The yield of the saturated hydrocarbon is considerably affected by the time of contact of the dione with the solution, formation of the intermediate reduction product (I), and amalgamated zinc. Probably dimedone is directly reduced to the hydrocarbon, more probably the intermediate diol (I) is reduced to the dihydro compound (IV, R-R'-OH), and (V), of which the former changes to dimethylcyclohexane (IV, R-R'-H), while the compound (V) passes into a ketone by the pinacolic transformation.

In order to settle the constitution of the trimethylcyclopentanone, a synthetic process starting with isoacetophorone appears to be a possible one. iso-Acetophorone is reduced to $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclohexanone and subsequently oxidised to an acid, rather difficult to purify. The acid on cyclisation gives a ketone which is, however, found to be different from $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone. On oxidation $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclohexanone could give either the acid (VI) or the acid (VII). The ketone should therefore be either $\alpha\gamma\gamma$ - or $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone. The semicarbazone of the ketone melts at a definite temperature and after several crystallisations it does not undergo any change. We were rather surprised when the melting point of the semicarbazone of the ketone differed from those of either $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ - or $\alpha\gamma\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone, and we proceeded to synthesise both these ketones by other unambiguous methods.

A very plausible method for the synthesis of the $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone appears to be the distillation of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipic acid or the cyclisation of the ester and subsequent hydrolysis. For the synthesis of this acid methylcyclohexanone has been methylated with sodamide and methyl iodide according to Haller and Cornubert (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1926, *iv*, 39, 1724). Subsequent methylation of dimethylcyclohexanone yields $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclohexanone. The oxidation of this ketone is expected to yield $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipic acid. The methylation of dimethylcyclohexanone could, however, take place at the alternative methylene group and yield symmetrical trimethylcyclohexanone (VIII, R-R'-H; R'-R'''-Me). The trimethylcyclohexanone obtained from the two consecutive methylations gives with benzaldehyde (Ruzicka, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1925, 9, 246) a very fine crystalline monobenzylidene compound (IX) which could not be obtained from the symmetrical compound. Hence the trimethylcyclohexanone should have the configuration (VIII, R-R'-Me; R'-R'''-H).

On oxidation the ketone (VIII, $R-R'-Me$; $R''-R'''-H$) gives a mixture of acids from which methylsuccinic acid and trimethyladipic acid could be separated by a few crystallisations. The identity of the trimethyladipic acid is confirmed by direct comparison with the acid, synthesised by Qudrat-i-Khuda and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 287) and is found to be absolutely identical. The corresponding ketone is obtained from this acid by cyclisation or from the ester, when the keto-carboxylic ester is obtained which yields $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone (X). The semicarbazone melts at 173° . The ketone is thus identical with that synthesised by Qudrat-i-Khuda and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*).

Attention has then been directed towards the synthesis of $\alpha\gamma\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone. Although it proved to be a rather difficult piece of work but ultimately we have been able to synthesise it. For this synthesis $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacetobutyric acid (XI) is converted into its cyanohydrin, when instead of the free cyanohydrin the corresponding lactonic nitrile (XII, $R = \text{CN}$) is obtained.

This is then hydrolysed to yield the lactonic acid (XII, $R = \text{COOH}$). The acid is esterified and is treated with phosphorus pentachloride and alcohol when the chloro-ester (XIII) is isolated.

As it has been found to be difficult to remove this chlorine is the lactonic acid (XII, $R = \text{COOH}$) is subjected to direct reduction with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus, when $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipic acid (VII) is obtained. Although this acid melts at the same temperature as that obtained previously, yet there is a marked depression of melting point when mixed with a sample of trimethyladipic acid prepared from $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclohexanone described earlier. On cyclisation the acid gives a ketone whose semicarbazone melts at 168° and there is no depression when this is mixed with the semicarbazone obtained from dimedone ketone. Thus the configuration of the ketone is definitely settled. It is expected that more interesting information may be obtained when other cyclic diones are examined later.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Dihydroisophorone was prepared by a suitable modification of Skita's method (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 1627) as follows :

*iso*Phorone (21 g.) and palladium chloride (0.6 g.) were mixed with distilled water (100 c.c.), heated till it dissolved, gum arabic (4 g.), dissolved in water (500 c.c.), alcohol (100 c.c.) and *isophorone* (21 g.), prepared by the method of Knoevenagel and Tricker (*Annalen*, 1887, 297, 185), were then added and the mixture was warmed to 80° and partially evacuated. It was then filled with pure hydrogen and shaken mechanically at the room temperature. At first the absorption was rapid and in course of 1 hour 2.5 litres were absorbed. The final absorption was 3.6 litres in course of 5 hours. Dihydroisophorone boiled at 76°/23 mm., yield 19 g. It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 204°.

Trimethyladipic Acid.—Dihydroisophorone (50 g.) was oxidised by adding it dropwise to warm nitric acid (200 c.c., *d* 1.4) in course of 2 hours. When the addition had been complete, it was heated on a water-bath for about 1½ hours. It was then poured into a shallow basin and concentrated. On cooling in ice, crystals separated out. The solid was separated from the mother-liquor and recrystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid. Finally it was crystallised once more from ether and petrol and the product melted at 72°. (Found : C, 51.9; H, 7.7. $C_7H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 52.4; H, 7.5 per cent).

A portion of the acid remained in the liquid state and could not be induced to crystallise. It was esterified by alcohol and sulphuric acid. The ester was found to boil at 155-57°/42 mm., yield 52 g from 50 g. of the acid. (Found : C, 63.3; H, 9.7. $C_{13}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 63.9; H, 9.8 per cent). n_D , 1.42376; $d_4^{31.5}$, 0.95610. (R_L)_D found, 64.98; calc. for $C_{13}H_{24}O_4$, 64.99.

A little of the ester was hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid and the oily product after purification through the sodium salt and drying was left in a vacuum desiccator for nearly a fortnight when it solidified. This was crystallised from dry ether and found to melt at 72. [Found (in the silver salt) : Ag, 53.6. $C_9H_{14}O_4Ag_2$ requires Ag, 53.7 per cent].

Trimethylcyclopentanone Carboxylate.—Trimethyladipic ester (50 g.) was added to a cooled solution of sodium ethoxide (9.8 g. sodium in 200 c.c. alcohol) and after 3 hours the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 8 hours. Excess of alcohol was removed and ice added. The oily layer was extracted with ether, and washed several times with water, dried (calcium chloride) and the product isolated in the usual way. Trimethylcyclopentanone carboxylate boiled at 102-103°/4 mm., yield 31 g. The semicarbazone crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 92°. (Found : C, 56.4; H, 8.2. $C_{12}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 56.5; H, 8.2 per cent). Ketone was regenerated from this semicarbazone by dilute hydrochloric acid (10%), b.p. 98°/4 mm. (Found : C, 66.3; H, 9.0. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.0 per cent). n_D , 1.42406; $d_4^{31.5}$, 0.9786. [R_L]_D found, 51.64; calc for $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$, 51.53.

Trimethylcyclopentanone.—(a) The above keto-carboxylic ester (25 g.) was hydrolysed by concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) on a sand-bath for 4 hours. The oily portion was extracted with ether, washed with a solution of sodium carbonate and water and dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate). Solvent was removed and distilled, b.p. 75-77°/45 mm., yield 12 g. It gave a semicarbazone very readily, which crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 155°. (Found: C, 59.0; H, 9.2. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 59.0; H, 9.4 per cent). The corresponding ketone was regenerated from the semicarbazone by heating it over a water-bath with dilute hydrochloric acid (10%), b.p. 76°/45 mm. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 11.0. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires C, 76.2; H, 11.1 per cent). n_D^{20} , 1.42175; d_4^{20} , 0.8828 [R_L] D found, 36.43; calc. for $C_8H_{14}O$, 36.78

(b) Trimethyladipic acid (10 g.) was intimately mixed with powdered baryta (0.7 g) and heated for 3½ hours in an air-bath first at 150°-160° and then at 300°-305° when an oily substance distilled over. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and water. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and water. It was dried and distilled and the ketone collected at 72°/42 mm, yield 3.6 g. It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 155°. It is identical with the previous one.

Synthesis of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone

Preparation of $\alpha\gamma$ -Dimethylcyclohexanone.—Methylcyclohexanone (22 g.) was slowly dropped on sodamide (10 g.), kept under dry ether (50 c. c.) in a three-necked flask provided with a mercury-sealed mechanical stirrer when a brisk evolution of ammonia began, and after the addition was complete (40 minutes), the flask was slightly warmed (33°) and kept warm for 2½ hours. When no more ammonia was evolved, the whole was cooled in ice, and methyl iodide (29 g., 12.6 c.c.) was added drop by drop and the mixture left overnight in a perfectly dry condition. Next day it was again warmed to 40° for 3 hours and then cooled in ice and ice-cold water was added to it from the dropping funnel. An oily layer separated which was collected and the aqueous portion was extracted twice with ether. The ethereal extract was then mixed with the original oil portion and the whole was washed with water, dilute hydrochloric acid, water, followed by a dilute solution of sodium thiosulphate and the solvent was removed. It was then fractionated under diminished pressure and dimethylcyclohexanone was found to boil at 90°/40 mm., yield 18 g. (*cf.* Haller and Cornubert. *loc. cit.*).

The semicarbazone crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 190°. A semicarbazone from 3-methylcyclohexanone was found to melt at 195° and a mixture of the two was found to melt at 176-77°.

Preparation of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclohexanone from Dimethylcyclohexanone.—This methylation was effected exactly on similar lines as before. Dimethylcyclohexanone (25 g.) was methylated with powdered sodamide (10 g.) in dry ether

and then warmed for 2½ hours. It was cooled and methyl iodide (26 g.) was added and the methylated product was isolated as before. The ketone boiled at 75°/25 mm. It formed a semicarbazone which crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 176°. (Found: C, 61.2; H, 9.6. $C_{10}H_{19}ON_3$ requires C, 60.9; H, 9.6 per cent). The ketone regenerated from the semicarbazone boiled at 72°/25 mm. (Found: C, 77.08; H, 11.4. $C_9H_{18}O$ requires C, 77.1; H, 11.4 per cent). $d_4^{33.6}$, 0.8778; n_D , 1.43691; $[R_L]_D$ found, 41.78; calc., 41.5 per cent.

Benzylidene compound of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclohexanone.—In a 500 c.c. three-necked flask provided with a mechanical stirrer was taken $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclohexanone (4 g.) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (12 g.), sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 40 c.c.) and rectified spirit (100 c.c.) and stirred for 3 days, keeping it at the room temperature. Water was then added to the mass after three days' stirring and the oil that separated was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed thrice with sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and steam distilled to remove the excess of benzaldehyde. The product after usual purification was treated with a little light petroleum (b. p. 40°). When solidified, it was crystallised from ether and light petroleum, m.p. 82°. (Found: C, 84.2; H, 8.7. $C_{14}H_{20}O$ requires C, 84.2; H, 8.8 per cent).

Oxidation of Trimethylcyclohexanone with Nitric Acid: Preparation of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Methyladipic Acid.—The ketone (30 g.) was dropped to a mixture of nitric acid (100 c.c.) and water (50 c.c.) previously heated on the water-bath. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours. The product was then poured into a shallow basin and concentrated on a water-bath. Water was added to it again and again till excess of nitric acid was completely removed. It was then kept inside a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride and caustic potash and after keeping for 7 days it solidified to a waxy mass. This was spread over a porous plate and the solid was crystallised from dry ether, m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 57.5; H, 8.5. $C_9H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 57.4; H, 8.5 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipate was obtained by esterification of trimethyladipic acid (66 g.) by heating on the water-bath for 12 hours with alcohol (300 c. c.) and sulphuric acid (30 c. c.). It was isolated as usual. b.p. 120-23°/10 mm., yield 75 g. (80% of theory). It was redistilled at 107°/3 mm. (Found: C, 63.6; H, 9.8. $C_{13}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 63.9; H, 9.8 per cent). $d_4^{33.6}$, 0.9318; n_D , 1.41706; $[R_L]_D$ found, 65.63; calc., 65.30.

Trimethylcyclopentane Carboxylate.—Trimethyladipic ester (50 g.) was added slowly to an ice-cold solution of sodium ethoxide (4.6 g. sodium and 100 c.c. alcohol). It was then heated on the water-bath for 10 hours. Alcohol was removed from the water-bath as far as possible and crushed ice added to it. It was next acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, and then with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and again with water. It was dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate) and solvent was removed. Trimethylcyclopentanone carboxylate boiled at 94°/3 mm., yield 31 g. (75% of the

theory). The *semicarbazone* was prepared by heating it with semicarbazide hydrochloride in aqueous methyl alcohol solution with sodium acetate for 1 hour. The alcohol was removed and pieces of ice were added to it when a sticky solid mass separated out which was kept over porous plates. The solid was removed after a few days and was crystallised from benzene and petrol (b.p. 55-60°) mixture, m.p. 85-88°. Ketonic ester was regenerated from this semicarbazone by heating with dilute hydrochloric acid (10%) till all the solid dissolved in the acid and a clear layer of ketonic ester was found floating on water. It was cooled and then saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted with ether. The ester was purified in the usual way, b.p. 93°/3 mm. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 9.1. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.1 per cent). d_4^{25} , 0.9712; n_D , 1.42666; $[R_L]_D$ found, 52.26; calc., 52.34.

Hydrolysis of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone Carboxylate: Preparation of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone.—A mixture of the keto-ester (20 g.) and hydrochloric acid (30%, 75 c.c.) and water (75 c.c.) was heated on a sand-bath for 4 hours, cooled and then thoroughly saturated with ammonium sulphate. It was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The oily residue boiled at 73°/42 mm., yield 6.5 g. (52% of the theory). It was purified through its semicarbazone, m.p. 173°. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 9.3. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 59.0; H, 9.3 per cent). $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone boiled at 72°/42 mm. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 11.08. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires C, 76.2; H, 11.1 per cent). d_4^{25} , 0.9661; n_D , 1.42126; $[R_L]_D$ found, 36.89; calc., 36.95.

$\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentane.—Powdered trimethyladipic acid (10 g.) was thoroughly mixed with finely powdered baryta (0.7 g.) and distilled from an air-bath kept at 160°-180° for nearly 1 hour. The temperature was slowly raised to 320°-330° when the ketone distilled. The distillate was collected and diluted with ether, the ethereal extract was washed with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and then with water and finally the solvent was removed and the oily residue was distilled at 70°/38 mm., yield 3.5 g. (53% of theory). The semicarbazone melted at 173° (mixed m.p. with the semicarbazone of the ketone prepared before). The ketone was regenerated from the semicarbazone by treating it with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracting with ether, b.p. 73°/42 mm.

Ethyl Carbethoxydimethyl-ketobutyrate.—To a well cooled solution of sodium ethoxide (2.3 g.) was added a mixture of malonic ester (160 g.) and mesityl oxide (98 g.). It was then heated on the water-bath for 6½ hours after which alcohol was removed and the condensation product was isolated by dilution with water and extraction with ether. It was dried by fused calcium chloride and the residue after removal of the solvent was collected at

178-180°/38 mm., yield 78 g. (38-40%). (Found: C, 60.5; H, 8.5. $C_{13}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 60.46; H, 8.51 per cent). $d_4^{33.5}$, 0.1029; n_D , 1.4335; $[R_L]_D$ found, 65.84; calc., 65.31.

ββ-Dimethyl-γ-acetylbutyric acid was prepared by the hydrolysis of ethyl carbethoxydimethylacetylbutyrate with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30%, 400 c.c.) by heating on a sand-bath for 6 hours. It was then concentrated under reduced pressure, cooled and extracted with a cold and dilute solution of sodium carbonate. A solid substance separated out which was filtered off, and crystallised from dilute alcohol and was found to be dimesone. The sodium carbonate extract was next acidified, saturated with ammonium sulphate (solid) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), the solvent removed, and the residual oily layer was kept in a vacuum desiccator, but could not be induced to solidify, yield 51 g. (84% of theory). [Found (in the silver salt): Ag, 40.5 $C_8H_{13}O_3Ag$ requires Ag, 40.8 per cent].

Dimethylhydroxycyanobutyric Acid and the corresponding Lactonic Acid.—

Ethyl dimethylacetylbutyrate, prepared from the acid, using alcohol and sulphuric acid, was treated with a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite, but no solid bisulphite compound could be separated. The ester was next treated with an aqueous solution of potassium cyanide, and subsequently with concentrated hydrochloric acid according to the method of Welch and Clemo (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2629). But it could not be converted into the cyanohydrin. The solution of the acid (20 g.) in water (125 c.c.) was taken inside a 3-necked flask provided with a mechanical stirrer and a dropping funnel. The third end was fitted with a glass tube which was led to an efficient air-suction. The flask was cooled in a mixture of ice and salt and a solution of potassium cyanide (60 g. in 100 c. c. of water) was slowly dropped into the solution of the acid during 2 hours. It was then left within the freezing mixture for 2 hours with continuous stirring, after which concentrated hydrochloric acid (94 c. c., 30%) was very slowly added from the dropping funnel during 4 hours. It was then kept in ice overnight; the cyanohydrin was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with water several times. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (120 c. c., 30%) by heating on the water-bath for 12 hours. The aqueous solution was concentrated under reduced pressure at the temperature of the water-bath. A solid acid separated out which was filtered off and crystallised from a mixture of ether and petrol (b. p. 55-60°), m. p. 81°. (Found: C, 50.79; H, 7.3. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.06; H, 7.5 per cent).

Reduction of the Lactonic Acid.—The lactonic acid (2 g.) was mixed with red phosphorus (1 g.) and hydriodic acid (d 1.9, 12 c. c.) and heated in a sealed tube for 16 hours at 150°-160°. The acid was isolated as a thick syrupy residue after careful purification and removal of the solvent. The residue was triturated with water and separated from a small insoluble solid and finally water was removed

on a water-bath and then left in a vacuum desiccator for about 2 weeks. The solid thus obtained crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid (30%), m. p. 71°. [Found: C, 57.3; H, 8.5. M. W. (by titration), 187.4. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 57.4; H, 8.5 per cent. M. W., 188].

Ethyl $\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethyladipate.—Trimethyladipic acid (12 g.) was esterified with absolute alcohol (80 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 4 c. c.) by heating over a water-bath for 4 hours. The ester was isolated as usual, b. p. 105°/4mm., yield 12 g. (75% of theory). (Found: C, 63.8; H, 9.7. $C_{13}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 63.9; H, 9.8 per cent). $d_4^{31.5}$, 0.9561; n_D , 1.42376; $[R_L]_D$ found, 64.98; calc., 64.99.

Ethyl $\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipate (10 g.) and molecular sodium (0.8 g.) in benzene were heated under reflux for 6 hours on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and the product decomposed by ice. It was acidified by concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water and then sodium carbonate solution and water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent removed and trimethyl $\alpha\gamma$ -cyclopentanone-carboxylate collected at 98°/4 mm. Its semicarbazone separated out as a sticky mass which solidified in course of a few days. It was crystallised from very dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 42°. (Found: C, 56.4; H, 8.2. $C_{12}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 56.5; H, 8.2 per cent). The ketone was regenerated from the semicarbazone, when it boiled at 98°/4 mm. (Found: C, 66.3; H, 9.0. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.0 per cent). $d_4^{31.5}$, 0.9786; n_D , 1.42406; $[R_L]_D$ found, 51.64; calc., 51.53.

$\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone.—Trimethylcyclopentanone carboxylate (10 g.) was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid (30%, 100 c. c.) and water (30 c. c.) by heating for 4 hours. The liquid was then washed with ice-cold water and saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate, water, dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), the solvent removed and the ketone collected at 75°/38 mm., yield 3.1 g (51% of theory). It gave a semicarbazone which crystallised from benzene, m. p. 168°. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 9.3. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 59.0; H, 9.3 per cent). The ketone was regenerated from the semicarbazone, b. p. 73°/37 mm. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 11.1. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires C, 76.1; H, 11.1 per cent). $d_4^{33.8}$, 0.8752; n_D , 1.42506; $[R_L]_D$ found, 86.82, calc; 36.95.

The same ketone was obtained by dry distillation of trimethyladipic acid (7 g.), intimately mixed with finely powdered baryta (0.7 g.) in an air-bath, kept at 180°. The temperature was gradually raised from 180°-310°, when the ketone was collected. The ketone thus obtained boiled at 73°/37 mm., yield 2.6 g. (52% of the theory). It gave a semicarbazone, m. p. 168° and was identical with the ketone obtained by the other method.

Monobenzylidene compound of $\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone was obtained by condensing the ketone (2 g.) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (6 c. c.) in presence of sodium hydroxide solution (10 c. c., 10%) by mechanically stirring the mixture with rectified spirit (30 c. c.) for 75 hours. The mixture was diluted with water (100 c.c.) and the oily substance was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide and the ether removed. The oily residue was distilled in steam and the residue in the flask dissolved in ether and purified in the usual way. The benzylidene compound solidified to a crystalline mass which crystallised from a mixture of dry ether and dry petrol, m.p. 76°. (Found : C, 83.9 ; H, 8.4. $C_{15}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.1 ; H, 8.4 per cent).

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